

Teaching typologies: Comparisons among the US and Swiss preservice teachers on their teaching typologies, motivational profiles and instructional beliefs

Recent international research in teacher education have examined the motivations and beliefs about teaching among prospective teachers as a mean to understand various aspects related to individual choices for a teaching career given the growing teacher shortages worldwide (Thomson et al., 2012, 2014; Watt & Richardson, 2008). Many countries experience acute teacher attrition and simultaneously the need for teaching quality. Examining the initial teacher motivations and beliefs of individuals pursuing a teaching career could help future research and educators understand other aspects indirectly related to teacher attrition, such as a mismatch between entry teaching reasons and job dissatisfaction, or cultural differences in motivations and beliefs about teaching. It is essential therefore to understand *prospective teachers' initial professional goals* for teaching, including their *teaching motivations, views about teaching* and their *pedagogical beliefs*.

Study purpose

The purpose of our study was to identify teaching motivations across different subsamples (typologies of preservice teachers from United States and Switzerland). Further, we explored the most influential motivations, teaching beliefs and pedagogical beliefs and how these constructs are comparable across subsamples from the United States and Switzerland. Very few studies in this area investigate prospective teachers' motivations and beliefs using a typological approach and attempting a cross-cultural comparison between the identified teaching typologies. Our study is a response to the scarcity such research in the teaching education field, using both a typological approach in understanding teachers' motivational profiles and a cross-cultural comparison of the identified typologies. Only one study (i.e., Watt, Richardson, Klusmann,

Kunter, Beyer, Trautwein, & Baumert, 2012) was identified as an international comparative study using a sophisticated study design with prospective teachers from different countries, but not a teacher typology comparison. Our research questions were:

1. What main teaching motivators can be identified among all participants and how do they differ with respect to each sample (i.e., US and Swiss sample)?
2. What teaching typologies can be identified in the two subsamples of prospective teachers (i.e., US and Swiss sample) based on their respective teaching motivational profiles? How do the two identified typologies (i.e., US and Swiss sample) differ with respect to their motivational profiles?
3. Across the two identified teaching typologies from the two subsamples, how do they differ with respect to their views about teaching and their pedagogical beliefs?

Teaching Motivations and Beliefs

Researchers commonly classify teaching motivators into intrinsic and extrinsic reasons, described as key reasons and values to teach along with individuals' perceptions of and commitment to the teaching career (i.e., Konig & Rothland, 2012; Watt et al., 2012). Some researchers (e.g., Kyriacou & Coulthard, 2000) have argued that individuals enter the teaching profession for one of three primary reasons, including altruistic reasons—such as the conception of teaching as a socially valuable profession—in addition to intrinsic and extrinsic reasons. Research findings from an expectancy-value perspective have found that the types of values and expectations of preservice teachers are crucial for their teaching choices, goal persistence, and the effort (i.e., Fokkens-Bruinsma & Canrinus, 2012; Parkes & Jones, 2012).

Studies exploring teaching motivation from an expectancy-value theory perspective have found that the types of values and expectations of preservice teachers are crucial for their

individual teaching choices, persistence in pursuing the teaching goal, and the effort invested in accomplishing their professional goals (Watt & Richardson, 2008).

Research findings from countries around the world show that teachers' motivations for teaching along with their beliefs about the teaching career and their perceptions of the pedagogy of teaching are at the core of teachers' professional identities, classroom decisions and their professional development (i.e., Lauermann, & Karabenick, 2011; Rinke, 2008). Studies exploring the relationship between teacher expectancies and ability beliefs and a range of outcome variables find these constructs to be strongly connected with motives for entering and persisting in the teaching profession, as well as engaging in professional development and implementing professional development-related initiatives.

Methodology

Sample

Data were collected using surveys from prospective teachers enrolled in professional courses in a teacher education program from the US and in Switzerland ($N=810$). Both samples, participants from the US ($n=327$) and participants from Switzerland ($n=483$) were enrolled in a teacher training program in a college of education (at a major university).

Measures

To examine prospective teachers' motivations for teaching and their beliefs about teaching we used the *FIT-choice scale* (Watt, & Richardson, 2007), a 62 item inventory on a 7-point Likert scale asking participants to rate their most influential motivations for teaching and their agreement with statements about the teaching profession. To examine prospective teachers' pedagogical beliefs we used the *Beliefs about teaching* (TALIS, OECD, 2009) a 8 item inventory

on a 7-point Likert scale asking participants to rate their agreement with pedagogical statements provided in the survey.

Results

Factor analyses and invariance testing

Multiple-group confirmatory factor analyses (M-G CFA) were performed in three parts: The 10 factors representing ability, task value, and social influences (32 items total) were first tested, followed by the 6 factors representing perceptions of teaching (19 items), dissuasion, and satisfaction with choice; finally the 2 factors representing pedagogical beliefs (8 items) were tested.

For the 32 motivation items, a 10-factor solution demonstrated satisfactory data fit¹: $\chi^2_{(876)} = 2068.04$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 2.36$ ($\chi^2_{US} = 1117.61$, $\chi^2_{Swiss} = 950.43$), CFI = 0.90, RMSEA = 0.06. Two second order factors, namely personal utility (saturating job security and time for family) value and social utility (saturating work with children/adolescents, make social contribution, enhance social equity, shape future of children/adolescents) value were modeled. Regarding perceptions of teaching, a 6-factor solution was found to fit the data adequately²: $\chi^2_{(295)} = 609.96$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 2.07$ ($\chi^2_{US} = 288.16$, $\chi^2_{Swiss} = 321.80$), CFI = 0.93, RMSEA = 0.05. Concerning pedagogical beliefs, a 2-factor solution was found to fit the data adequately³: $\chi^2_{(22)} = 50.03$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 2.27$ ($\chi^2_{US} = 13.66$, $\chi^2_{Swiss} = 36.37$), CFI = 0.95, RMSEA = 0.06. This solution required to remove two items weakly loading on the factors.

In sum, the M-G CFA revealed five categories of motivations (i.e., factors) across all data ($N=810$) as being influential on individuals' choices to become teachers. These factors were: aptitude, intrinsic value, opportunity, personal utility, and social utility. Furthermore, six types of perceptions were identified: Expertise, high demand, social status, salary, social dissuasion, and

satisfaction with choice. Finally, two types of pedagogical beliefs were found: constructivism and direct transmission.

Motivation and beliefs differences across samples

In both samples, intrinsic value, ability, and social utility value were rated as more important than personal utility value and opportunity. There were nonetheless mean differences across the samples. Comparison of factor means revealed that US preservice teachers rated the importance of all five motivation factors as significantly (all $p < .001$) higher than Swiss VET teachers do (standardized factor mean differences: 0.40 for aptitude, 0.82 for intrinsic value, 0.51 for time for family, 0.30 for job security, 0.88 for enhance social equity, 1.27 for make social contribution, 0.66 for work with children/adolescent, 0.69 for social influences, 0.87 for prior teaching and learning experiences). The only exception was opportunity which was higher in the Swiss sample (factor mean difference = 1.29).

Concerning perceptions of teaching, US preservice teachers reported that both task demand and social dissuasion were stronger (standardized factor mean differences of 0.78 and 1.37 respectively), whereas good salary was rated lower than in the Swiss sample (standardized factor mean difference = 1.88; all $p < .001$). Expertise, social status, and satisfaction with choice did not differ significantly across samples. Finally, direct transmission beliefs were rated higher in the Swiss sample than in the US sample (standardized factor mean difference = 1.36; $p < .001$) and constructivist beliefs did not differ.

Teaching typologies

US Teaching Typologies. A two-steps cluster analysis was performed (on the five factors from FIT-choice scale) separately for each subsample (US and Swiss participants). Five distinctive typologies (clusters) of individuals (N 's of 34, 54, 80, 72 and 85) were identified for

the US sample, indicating that specific sets of motivations were relevant for their teaching career choices. These typologies were labeled as: cluster 1 "High personal value", cluster 2 "Low intrinsic value", cluster 3 "High intrinsic value", cluster 4 "Opportunistic" and cluster 5 "Combined motivations". Figure 1 presents the 2-steps clustering profiles for 5 cluster solution (and motivational profiles based on the five motivation factors) for US participants ($n=327$).

Swiss Teaching Typologies. Five distinctive typologies (clusters) of individuals (n 's of 51, 111, 99, 172 and 170), labeled as cluster 1 "Maladaptive motivations", cluster 2 "Low opportunities", cluster 3 "High personal utility", cluster 4 "High opportunity" and cluster 5 "Multiple motivations" were identified for the Swiss sample. Figure 2 presents the 2-steps clustering profiles for 5 cluster solution (and motivational profiles based on the five motivation factors) for the Swiss participants ($n=483$).

For both the Swiss and the US identified typologies their motivational profiles indicated that similar specific sets of motivations were relevant for their teaching career choices as well as for the US sample (except the typology C5 "Multiple motivations").

US-Swiss Typologies: Comparisons

Inspections of means and standard deviations from participants' survey responses indicated that many similarities across the samples were identified with respect to rating *teaching motivations* (i.e., high ratings on intrinsic motivations, ability, work with young people), but *antecedent socializations* (i.e., prior teaching experience, social dissuasion) and *teaching beliefs* (i.e., high demand, good salary) varied between the two samples (see Table 1 and Figure 3).

Discussion

The interplay of different types of teaching motivations was unique for each identified teaching typology, however similarities in motivational profiles (US and Swiss samples) were

evident. Most influential motivational factors for participants' teaching choices were similar for the two samples (i.e., high personal values, social values, intrinsic values), but others were dissimilar and specific only for one subsample or certain identified typologies (i.e., perceived opportunity). Also, study findings suggests that at some level all participants had similar motivations for teaching, but different antecedent socializations and perceptions of teaching career (possibly due to cultural contexts of each country). Several international studies have shown that one's motivation for teaching and beliefs about teaching can vary across different contexts. These variations are reflecting the sociocultural contexts in different countries that could shape individuals' teaching views. Study findings can help teacher educators identify initial motivations and teaching views and help teachers develop professionally. In the US reforms introduced two decades ago emphasize the need to place more qualified and motivated teachers in the field to increase students' academic achievements; to do so, teachers need to be better prepared in their teaching education programs, helped to develop professionally and develop positive attitudes towards teaching (AEEE, 2005; NCTQ, 2004;NCTA,2007).

Teacher education programs may also benefit by tailoring teacher training programs to psychologically-based typologies of teachers (see Author et al., 2014). Efforts can be taken to better align coursework and field experiences with prospective teachers' beliefs, expectations, and values, while at the same time proving preservice teachers with the opportunities for these psychological attributes to be challenged as well as informed by the range of contexts that can potentially comprise a teaching career.

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Footnotes

1. Configural invariance was first assessed by performing identical CFA models separately for each sample: (US: $\chi^2_{(419)} = 1201.94$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 2.87$, CFI = .87, RMSEA = .08; Swiss $\chi^2_{(419)} = 1023.68$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 2.44$, CFI = .93, RMSEA = .05). Then, a fully-constrained multigroup model was tested: $\chi^2_{(882)} = 2439.01$ [$\chi^2_{US} = 1341.56$, $\chi^2_{Swiss} = 1097.44$], $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 2.77$, CFI = .87, RMSEA = .07. Comparison of this later model with the final model using the Satorra-Bentler scaled difference test (Satorra & Bentler, 2001) indicates a significant improvement in model fit: $\chi^2_{(6)} = 370.97$, $p < .001$.
2. Configural invariance was first assessed by performing identical CFA models separately for each sample: (US: $\chi^2_{(296)} = 553.55$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 1.87$, CFI = .94, RMSEA = .04; Swiss $\chi^2_{(296)} = 483.95$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 1.64$, CFI = .92, RMSEA = .04). Then, a fully-constrained multigroup model was tested: $\chi^2_{(300)} = 941.62$ [$\chi^2_{US} = 456.88$, $\chi^2_{Swiss} = 484.75$], $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 3.14$, CFI = .86, RMSEA = .07. Comparison of this later model with the final model using the Satorra-Bentler scaled difference test (Satorra & Bentler, 2001) indicated a significant improvement in model fit: $\chi^2_{(5)} = 331.66$, $p < .001$.

3. Again, configural invariance was first assessed by performing identical CFA models separately for each sample: (US: $\chi^2_{(8)} = 29.39$, $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 3.67$, CFI = .94, RMSEA = .07; Swiss $\chi^2_{(8)} = 8.03$, $p = 1$, CFI = 1, RMSEA < .01). Then, a fully-constrained multigroup model was tested: $\chi^2_{(24)} = 123.08$ [$\chi^2_{US} = 72.08$, $\chi^2_{Swiss} = 50.59$], $p < .001$, $\chi^2/df = 5.13$, CFI = .82, RMSEA = .10. Comparison of this later model with the final model using the Satorra-Bentler scaled difference test (Satorra & Bentler, 2001) indicated a significant improvement in model fit: $\chi^2_{(14)} = 73.05$, $p < .001$.

Figure 1. US typologies and motivational patterns (n=327)

Figure 2. Swiss typologies and motivational patterns (n=483)

Figure 3. US and Swiss samples comparisons on motivations and beliefs (N=810)

Table 1. Teaching motivations and beliefs survey results ($N=810$)

Scale	# Items	Swiss VET teachers ($n = 483$)		US student teachers ($n = 327$)	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
<i>Motivation</i>					
Intrinsic career value	4	5.94	0.89	5.73	1.16
Ability	3	5.46	0.97	5.81	1.05
Enhance social equity	2	4.52	1.48	5.70	1.32
Shape future of young people	2	5.19	1.07	6.12	1.11
Make social contribution	3	5.28	1.24	5.96	1.16
Work with young people	4	3.94	1.50	6.12	1.09
Job security	3	3.16	1.47	4.28	1.40
Time for family	5	4.39	1.20	3.82	1.43
Opportunity	3	4.39	1.20	3.21	1.51
<i>Antecedent socialization</i>					
Prior teaching and teaching experiences	3	4.39	1.56	5.64	1.28
Social influences	3	2.65	1.60	3.93	1.66
Social dissuasion	4	2.52	1.42	4.64	1.62
<i>Perceptions of teaching</i>					
High demand	3	5.53	0.96	6.12	0.94
Expert career	2	5.86	0.92	5.54	1.15
Good salary	2	4.72	1.38	2.15	1.23
Social status & Teacher morale	6	4.31	1.03	4.03	1.27